
PARENTING STYLE AND STUDENTS' CONFORMITY TO SCHOOL RULES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the relationship between parenting styles and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. To achieve the aim of the study, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Correlational research design was used for the study. The study population consisted of all the 14,583 students in Senior Secondary Two classes (SS 2) in the 86 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. Five hundred and eighty three senior secondary two (SS 2) students were selected from 17 public secondary schools in the area for the study using Simple random sampling technique. Parenting Styles and Students' Conformity to school Rules Questionnaire (PSSCSRQ) was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using internal consistency method. The TPSSCSRQ was subjected to Cronbach Alpha Analysis and the reliability index of 0.82 was obtained. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistic was used to analyze the data. The r-coefficient was used to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that, authoritative and permissive parenting Styles significantly relate to students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. It is recommended amongst others that, parents should show good example to their children on how to conform to rules at home so that students can replicate this in schools.

Keywords: Parenting Style, Students' Conformity, School Rules, Secondary Schools, Akwa Ibom North-East, Nigeria

Introduction

Family is the fundamental and important structure of the society that has an important role in one's life and in the society. The importance of proper parenting in the family as a social structure is undeniable. Although affected by society and peers, children are influenced by parents in the family. The influence of the family on the child and its roles in the creativity, cultural, social, and moral aspects are very great and important. When a child is born into a family, such a child is helpless and needs the help of others to get on. These others are usually the members of the family or the caregivers. The major caregivers are usually the parents.

A parent is a person who fosters all facets of a child's growth by nourishing, protecting, and guiding the child through the course of development (Eze, 2016). Operationally, a parent is one who has the duty of transferring values, norms and experiences that could influence the child in the society because parents exert the first influence on the children's life before any other factor. Thus, parent shape the character and personality of their children through the process of parenting. Parenting is the act of moulding, shaping, guiding, and supporting the development of an individual from infant to adulthood. Parenting is carried out differently by individuals because of differences in personalities and exposure, giving rise to different parenting styles.

Parenting style can be defined as a set or a system of behaviours that describes the parent and child interactions over a wide range of situations and creates an effective interaction atmosphere (Maher and Komajani, 2016). Kelland (2020) observes that where an ideal parenting style is employed in the home, the children are disciplined but where this is not, the reverse is the case. It is common sense to say that parenting style plays an important role in a child's growth. In the context of this study, parenting styles are the representation of how parents respond to the demands of their children. Many authors have presented different forms of parenting styles but for the purpose of this study, the researcher is considering authoritative, permissive styles of parenting.

Authoritative parents are warm and communicate well with the children. The parents are both responsive to the needs of the children and demanding in that they set expectations for the children. Munyi (2013) noted that this type of parenting style permits children enough freedom of expression so that they can develop a sense of independence without extending beyond reasonable limits. They are firm, consistent, and fair. They establish and enforce behaviour standards and stay in control by encouraging their children to follow the standard. Family rule is democratic rather than dictatorial. In authoritative parenting, children's opinions are valued and respected. Such Parents are encouraged to decide and accept responsibility for their actions and decisions (Cherry, 2015). In addition, it can be said that such parents are more likely to encourage academic success. Areepattamannil (2016) found a positive and significant relationship between authoritative parenting and academic achievement. Furthermore, the study reported that authoritative parenting involved rewarding learning-related behaviours with encouragement and praise but did not ignore punishment for doing otherwise

Permissive parents on the other hand are high in warmth but lack control towards the children. Permissive parents are more responsive to the needs of the children but less demanding. Permissive parents are lenient, do not require mature behaviour, allow considerable self-regulation and avoid confrontation (Sarac, 2014). Such parents find it hard to set clear limits and provide structure. Permissive parents tend to reward bad behaviour

regularly. Children are not pushed to obey guidelines or standards such that even when they do exist, they are not enforced. Tilahun (2012) found in a study that students who perceived their parents as permissive had significantly lower academic achievement and psychosocial adjustment compared to their counterparts who rated their parents as authoritative. Kambo (2016) who found that permissive parenting was negatively associated with higher academic achievement, which is most likely the result of the parents' lack of control and discipline over their children. Permissive parents take orders and instructions from their children; and are passive, endow children with power, have low expectations, use minimal discipline and do not feel responsible for how their children turn out. Ironically, these children turn out to be the unhappiest of all. Such children are more likely to exhibit such psychological problems as anxiety and depression. Research links permissive parents with delinquency, substance abuse, and sexual activities (Sailor, 2013).

It is common to say that some parenting styles do not favour good achievement orientation and academic achievement while others do. Some researchers such as Kimble(2014) and Baumrind (2019) have argued that interaction between children and parents and how parents communicate with children are considered to be the most important and fundamental factors among the various factors that affect children's conformity to rules and a healthy character.

Rules also known as standards of behaviour can be defined as the shared expectations of a group of people. These include what the group regards as a socially acceptable pattern of behaviour expected of every individual in the group. Ideally, schools set rules and regulations for the proper governing of the various lifestyles of students containing the dos and don'ts (Okumbe, 2018). In most cases it follows with school regulations. Regulations on the other hand are authoritative orders with a course of law intended to promote order and efficiency in an organization such as school. The disciplinary standards of the school can be seen in how effective schools demonstrate sound inclusive practices, which includes emphasizing school rules and regulations, collaborative leadership and their good practice. The school rules and regulations therefore prescribe the standard of behaviour expected of the teachers and the students. Good discipline at home as enforced by parents plays a vital role in students' conformity to school rules.

Conformity means to comply with rules (norms), standards or laws and to behave according to the usual standards of behaviour that are expected by a group in a society. Non-conformity to laid-down rules can be referred to as a deviance. Akarowhe (2018) viewed as a behavioural disposition that is not in conformity with an institutionalized set-up or code of conduct. Okorodudu (2012) noted that one may conform or accept influence because the person hopes to achieve a favourable reaction from another person or group. The individual adopts the induced behaviour not because such believes in its content but because the person expects to gain specific rewards or approval and avoid specific punishments or disapproval by not conforming.

A person's upbringing has a profound influence on how the person sees the world and how the person processes information. Stevenson (2018) observed that different students view education as having different goals. This means that parenting can create a pool of informed citizens with a developed ability to think and reason and it can be used to establish students who share a common body of knowledge and who share socialization into the way things are done in a particular society. Studies by DeVore and Ginsburg (2015), Spera (2015), and Baumrind (2019) indicated that when parents use socially acceptable practices, children not

only develop optimally but are able to delay or moderate involvement in socially unacceptable behaviours.

Furthermore, Pachan (2012) opined that when parental values, rules, communication, discipline management strategies are effective, children gain from it in their behavioral conduct; while negative peer pressure has been positively linked to students indiscipline. Devine, Ho and Wilson (2014) posit that children who feel loved and appreciated by parents and family develop high self-concept and are not only able to resist negative peer influence but also set boundaries for behavior that enable them realize full potential. Similarly, Changelwa, Ndurumo, Barasa and Poi Poi, (2014) state that such students avoid behaviours likely to hurt parents and family due to attachment held with them. This follows that acceptable standards of discipline will be upheld by the students.

Devine, Ho and Wilson (2014) state that children exposed to clear rules at home had no problem following rules at schools, Pachan and Molly (2012) in contrary, opine that stern parenting characterized by many rules could lead to indiscipline in students since they only obey to avoid negative consequences. Schools in their efforts have tried to enforce students' conformity to school rules. Yet, the problem of non-conformity to school rules still persist, the problem of non-conformity to school rules may be blamed on poor parenting styles at homes. It is against this background that this study sought to determine the relationship between parenting styles and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Management of students discipline through conformity to school rules seems to pose an increased challenge in many schools in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general as indicated by waves of bullying, arson, and vandalism of school property. Despite attempts by governments and school principals to ensure high moral standards through enforcement of school rules and regulations; there are still high rates of students' non-conformity to school rules. Schools in their efforts have tried to change the narratives yet, the problem of students' non-conformity to school rules still persists. The problem of non-conformity to school rules may be blamed on factors such as adolescence behavior, peer influence, youthful exuberance, environmental influence, and social media but the researcher sees poor parenting at homes as the major factor. The researcher sees the use of different parenting styles such as authoritative and permissive Styles as variables that can be used to get students conformed to school rules. It is against this problem that this study sought to determine the relationship between parenting styles and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the relationship between parenting styles and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. Specifically, this study sought:

1. To investigate the relationship between authoritative parenting Style and Students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools.
2. To explain the relationship between permissive parenting Style and Students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools?
2. What is the relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools?

Hypotheses of the Study

The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in secondary schools.

Methodology

This study adopted the correlational research design. The area for this study was Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is bounded to the west by Rivers State and Abia State, to the East by Cross River State, to the North again by Abia State and to the South by Atlantic Ocean. The population of the study consists of all the 14,583 students in Senior Secondary Two (SS-2) class in the 86 public secondary schools for 2022/2023 session in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. The sample size for this study consisted of 583 Senior Secondary Two students drawn from 17 public secondary schools in the area using proportionate Stratified and simple Random sampling techniques. The researcher developed instrument titled: Parenting Styles and Students' Conformity to school Rules Questionnaire (PSSCSRQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two section, A and B. Section A contained statements designed to gather information from students on the different Parenting Styles used by their parents at home. Section B contained statements on students' conformity to school rules. The instrument had a total of 20 items measured using a four point rating scale with response categories of: SA= Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree. The face validation of the instruments were determined by presenting the title, purpose of the study and research questions with copies of the instrument to three expert who are lecturerstwo experts in Social Studies and Citizenship Education, and one from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, Uyo. The comments, corrections and suggestions made by the experts were taken to consideration in drafting the final copies of the instrument. Reliability indices of 0.82 and 0.86 were obtained for sections A and B respectively using Cronbach Alpha Statistic. The researcher with the help of two research assistance administered the instrument using direct delivery method. The exercise lasted for two weeks to ensure a high return rate. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics was used to answer the research questions and in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rule in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District?

Table 4.1: Results of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in public secondary schools (N=510)

Variable	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	Remark
	$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Authoritative parenting style	7810	156344	461183	0.82	HR
Conformity to school rule	24975	1830023			

HR= High relationship

Result in Table 4.1 shows that the calculated r-value is 0.82. This indicates a high and positive relationship between authoritative parenting and students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. This implies that authoritative parenting relates with students' conformity to school rules in public secondary schools. The positive relationship occurs because increase in use of authoritative parenting styles by parents is accompanied by an increase in students' conformity to school rules.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in public secondary schools?

Table 4.2: Result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules (N=510)

Variable	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	Remark
	$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Permissive parenting styles	11696	347982	684864	-0.81	HR
Conformity to school rule	24975	1830023			

HR= High relationship

Result in Table 4.2 shows that the calculated r-value is 0.81. This indicates a high and negative relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school. This implies that permissive parenting style relates with students' conformity to school rules. The negative relationship occurs because increase in use of permissive parenting styles by parents is accompanied by a decrease in students' conformity to school rules.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and Students' conformity to school rules in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Table 4.3: Result Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules

Variable	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	r-crit.	Decision at P < 0.05
Authoritative parenting style	7810	156344	461183	0.82	0.08	* H ₀ Rejected
Students' academic performance	24975	1830023				

* =significant at P < .05 level, df = 508; N= 510; r-crit. 0.08

Result in Table 4.3 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.82 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.08 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 508 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis that state that there is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District

Table 4.4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules

Variable	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	r-crit.	Decision at P < 0.05
Permissive parenting	11696	347982	684864	0.81	0.08	* H ₀ Rejected
Students' academic performance	24975	1830023				

*significant at P < .05 level, df = 508; N= 510; r-crit. 0.08

Result on Table 4.4 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.81 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.08 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 508 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules is rejected. This implies that there is a

significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the finding showed a high and positive relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules. Also, there is a significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. The finding is in line with the earlier study conducted by Sutton (2016) who asserted that self-reflection, insight, and mindfulness which are aspect of authoritative parenting style can benefits students and make them to conform to rules at home and in school. The result also agrees with the findings of Areepattamannil (2016) who found a positive and significant relationship between authoritative parenting and academic achievement. Furthermore, the study reported that authoritative parenting involved rewarding learning-related behaviours with encouragement and praise but did not ignore punishment for doing otherwise. This shows that authoritative parenting style is essential for optimal daily life activities, as it allows adapting individuals behaviour to different situations according to one's actual abilities. This could either prevent risky or withdrawal behaviour among students that may lead to non-conformity to rules. In other words, authoritative parenting style allows students know what their limitations are and allows them to make choices based on their capabilities.

The result of the finding also showed a high and negative relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules. There is a significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' conformity to school rules. The outcome of the finding could be attributed to the fact that permissive parenting style permits children to go out and return anytime they like, such parents do not view themselves as responsible for guiding students' behaviours; they do not create time to be involved in their children education.

The finding is in line with the earlier study conducted by Tilahun (2012) who found in a study that students who perceived their parents as permissive had significantly lower academic achievement and psychosocial adjustment compared to their counterparts who rated their parents as authoritative. The finding is in line with the findings of Kambo (2016) who found that permissive parenting was negatively associated with higher academic achievement, which is most likely the result of the parents' lack of control and discipline over their children. This means that permissive parent's non-punitive and accepting approach toward their children's desires did not assist the children in building appropriate educational foundation but, rather, harmed their potential for academic success.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parenting styles significantly relate with students' conformity to school rules in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. Authoritative parenting style relate positively while permissive parenting style had a negative relationship with students' conformity to school rules.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and conclusions reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should embrace authoritative parenting style and to spend quality time with their children in order to monitor them for any signs of forms of delinquent behavior.
2. Parents should give education at home to their children from early childhood in addition to what they receive in school. Parents should also show good example to their children on how conformity to rules should be possible in school.

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